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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the deliverable

This document constitutes the ARCAFF Trained AR Localization and Classification DNNs report, first deliverable of Work Package 3 (*Deep Learning*), whose role within ARCAFF is the one of developing and applying advanced deep learning techniques to the enhanced solar data sets prepared within Work Package 2 (*Solar Sources*) activities.

Two different datasets, described in deliverable D2.2, have been released, so far, by WP2. The first dataset consists of a catalogue of 57,574 active region cutouts with associated magnetic/mcintosh classes, to serve as input and classification labels for a supervised learning approach to active region classification. The second dataset consists of a catalogue of 3,478 full-disk images, together with the bounds of 8,268 bounding boxes to train supervised region detection models able to localize and classify ARs in full disk magnetograms.

The primary objective of this report is to provide a detailed description of the work done so far within WP3, which includes

- the identification of the deep learning models most suitable for classification of AR cutouts (first objective of the project) and for localization and classification of ARs from full disk images (second objective of the project), among those proposed in the Grant Agreement, and beyond;
- detailed analysis of the two datasets released by WP2;
- training, test and performance analysis of the trained models on both datasets.

With respect to deep learning models, all models that had been cited in the ARCAFF proposal have been considered and described. Further, for the solution of the first problem, new promising approaches based on Transformers have been also identified, described and utilized.

As for the analysis of the available data, a thorough statistical analysis of the first dataset has been performed, which revealed the presence of some problems in the images and/or in the labelling that may limit the learning and, consequently, generalization capabilities of the learning models. Some of these problems appear to plague the second dataset as well. WP2 is working on solving these problems with the release of new updated datasets.

Lastly, the architectures of the models used, together with evaluations of the performance according to metrics and skill scores commonly used in the Machine Learning/Deep Learning literature, are reported in detail for both problems.

1.2 References

1.3 Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACC	Accuracy
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Average Precision
AR	Active Region
ARs	Active Regions
CLS	Classification
C2f	Fast CSP Bottleneck with 2 convolutions
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CNNs	Convolutional Neural Networks
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSI	Critical Success Index
CSP	Cross Spatial Partail
DeiT	Data-efficient Image Transformers
DL	Deep Learning
DNNs	Deep Neural Networks
FC	Fully Connected
FLOPS	FLoating point Operations Per Second
GFLOPS	Giga FLOPS (10^9 FLOPS)
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HMI	Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (onboard SDO)
HSS	Heidke Skill Score
IoU	Intersection over Union
mAP	Mean Average Precision
MDI	Michelson Doppler Imager (onboard SoHO)

MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OS	Operating System
QS	Quiet Sun
RAM	Random Access Memory
R-CNN	Region-based Convolutional Neural Network
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
ResNet	Residual Network
SDO	Solar Dynamics Observatory
SoHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPPF	Spatial Pyramid Pooling Faster
SRS	Solar Region Summary
SVM	Support Vector Machine
Swin Trasformer	Shifted Window Trasformer
TSS	True Skill Score
VGG	Visual Geometry Group
ViT	Vision Transformer
YOLO	You Only Look Once
WP	Work Package

2. Active region classification using magnetogram cutouts

2.1 Dataset

In order to achieve the first objective of the project,

Objective 1 (O1) - Active region classifications using magnetogram cutouts

WP2 has created a dataset including a set of ARs cutouts extracted from full-disk MDI/HMI observations by exploiting NOAA SRS information, alongside a set of random quiet sun regions that describe locations on the Sun that are not NOAA ARs. Each active region cutout has associated magnetic/mcintosh classes. The dataset consists of a catalogue of 57,574 rows of data corresponding to 106,125 cutout fits files and 7,535 quick look images. The catalogue, cutout fits files and quick look image were put at disposal to WP3 as a single compressed tar archive ‘*arccnet-cutout-dataset-v20231027.tar.gz*’.

2.1.1 Statistical analysis

Before training the models described in section 2.2, we performed a thorough statistical analysis of the data in the dataset. We first focused on an analysis of how it was inherently unbalanced. Figure 1 shows the distribution of classes within the dataset, according to the magnetic classification.

Figure 1 Distribution of the classes in the dataset.

The histogram shows that the dataset is very unbalanced, with a large number of Quiet Sun (QS) cutouts making up more than 62% of the dataset. The α (unipolar sunspot group) and β (bipolar sunspot group with a simple division between the polarities) classes together make up about 33%, while the remaining classes, corresponding to more complex configurations, do not reach 5%. In particular the classes γ (complex region in which the polarities are so irregularly distributed that they can't be classified as a bipolar sunspot group) and $\gamma - \delta$ (sunspot group with a γ magnetic configuration but containing one or more δ sunspots) have been excluded from the classification task given the low number of data available (8 in total). Further, for classification purposes, the classes $\beta - \gamma$ (bipolar sunspot group complex enough so that no line can be drawn between spots of opposite polarity), $\beta - \gamma - \delta$ (sunspot group with $\beta - \gamma$ magnetic configuration containing one or more δ sunspots) and $\beta - \delta$ (sunspot group with a general β magnetic configuration containing one or more δ sunspots) have been considered both separately and aggregated into a single class $\beta - X$.

Referring to the origin of AR cutouts, Figure 2 shows that for the α and β -X classes the data are fairly well distributed between MDI and HMI, while for the β class most of the data come from MDI. Figure 3, on the other hand, shows the number of AR in individual quick look images as a function of time, with a peak of 13 ARs during maximum solar activity of the 23rd cycle.

Figure 2 Origin of the AR cutouts.

Figure 3 Number of AR as a function of time in each image.

Much of the work in analysing the dataset consisted of looking for possible sources of deception for the learning models. Five different types of problems have been identified:

- Overlapping ARs boxes.** When several ARs are present in the same image, it may happen that different ARs are present in the same cutout, and, as a result, the same AR (or part of it) may be present in different cutouts with different labels. An example is provided in Figure 4, where cutouts containing ARs 8408 and 8412, as well as those containing ARs 8409 and 8406, turn out to be almost completely overlapping. This can be a significant source of error for a supervised learning model because in the presence of the same input it receives conflicting information about what the expected

output, to be learned, should be. Since this is an unsolvable problem that characterizes our data, we will focus on the design of specific training strategies.

Figure 4 Issue 1: Overlapping ARs boxes

- AR beyond solar limb.** A second source of mistake is the presence of ARs located near the right limb of the Sun. Considering sequences of images in time, it may happen that some cutouts are labelled as containing ARs even when the AR has moved beyond the solar limb and is no longer visible in the magnetogram. An example is provided in Figure 5, where AR 8103, well present and visible in the left image, is no longer visible in the right image corresponding to 24 hours later. This kind of cutouts, labelled as containing AR, but actually corresponding to quiet sun, can mislead the classifier who mistakenly learns to classify cutouts of type QS as ARs.

Figure 5 Issue 2: AR beyond solar limb.

- AR labelled as QS (i.e. plage regions).** A third source of error is the presence of *plages*, i.e., active regions that are correctly labelled as ARs at the beginning of an image sequence but are later re-labelled as Quiet Sun. An example is presented in Figure 6, in which the active region 8411 in the left panel becomes QS cutout with number 9 the following day (right panel). As in the previous case, the classifier could be misled in the training phase by incorrectly labelled cutouts. Unlike before, the classifier now sees as input cutouts labelled as QS, but which are corresponding to actual ARs instead.

Figure 6 Issue 3: Presence of plage regions.

- Problematic Magnetograms.** A relevant source of error is the presence of corrupted magnetograms in the database. We identified four different forms of bad data, summarized in Figure 7. In the upper left panel, an example of a completely corrupted magnetogram is presented. In the upper right panel, on the other hand, we observe a magnetogram with a swirling effect more evident toward the edges of the solar disk. A magnetogram in which only noise is present is shown in the lower left panel. Eventually, in the lower right panel, a rotated magnetogram is observed in which there is no correspondence between the cutouts highlighted in the image and the presence of QS or ARs.

Figure 7 Issue 4: Problematic magnetograms.

- Horizontal bars in cutouts.** The last class of problems concerns the presence of groups of rows in the image where data is identically zero. This results in the presence of uniform horizontal bars in the image (and thus in the cutouts extracted from it) that may alter the signal of a QS (top left panel of Figure 8) or, in the worst case, may cross an AR corrupting its information (bottom left panel of Figure 8). We did an in-depth study of the entire dataset to understand how much this effect was present in the images, and the result is shown in the right panel of Figure 8. This panel shows the number of images that have horizontal bars across the timespan of the dataset. Such bars may be due to the problem described before or to QS cutouts at the top or at the bottom of the solar disk. This is a problem affecting the entire dataset, with a greater impact on the MDI images but also present in the HMI images. This type of problem has a major impact in automatically recognizing ARs whose morphology may be severely altered from the real one.

Figure 8 Issue 5: Presence of horizontal bars in cutouts images.

The first three classes of problems, and the presence of horizontal bars in the cutouts, equally affect both HMI and MDI images, while the presence of problematic magnetograms in the cutouts would seem to affect only MDI images. As said at the beginning of the subsection, this kind of pathologies in the training set can limit the optimization of hyperparameters of the learning models. For this reason, the results of the statistical analysis performed by WP3 have been shared with WP2. All reported problems have been addressed and some of them already solved. As a result of this feedback action and the corrections made, WP2 released an updated version of the dataset in mid-July. In this new dataset, a new label for plage regions has been introduced, meaning they no longer appear in QS cutouts. The presence of bad data has been reduced and, during training on the new dataset, ARs will be filtered based on longitude information to prevent issues with ARs beyond the solar limb. However, in the following just the results we obtained on the original dataset are presented. Re-training of the networks on the new version of the dataset is currently in progress.

2.2 Deep Learning models

In order to achieve *Objective 1*, in the ARCAFF proposal we identified the following CNN architectures from DL literature:

- **AlexNet**, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with large learning capacity made of 5 convolutional layers + 3 fully-connected layers and variable size convolutional kernels (Krizhesky, Sutskever, & Hinton, 2012).
- **Visual Geometry Group (VGG)**, a deep learning architecture developed by the Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford and introduced in 2015 as a refinement of the AlexNet network (Simonyan & Zisserman, 2015). Known for its simplicity and uniform architecture, VGG primarily consists of 16 (VGG-16) or 19 (VGG-19) layers, including convolutional layers, max-pooling layers, and fully connected layers.

Figure 9 VGG-16 network, made of 13 convolutional layers + 3 fully connected layers and 3x3 filters replacing the variable size convolutional kernels used in AlexNet.

- **ResNetXX**, a network architecture made of 'XX' number of layers where the most commonly used ones are ResNet50 and ResNet101 (He, Zhang, Ren, & Sun, Deep residual learning for image recognition, 2016). ResNet, short for Residual Network, is a deep learning architecture designed to train very deep neural networks by addressing the vanishing gradient problem. ResNet utilizes residual learning by incorporating skip connections, or shortcuts, that bypass one or more layers. These skip connections allow the network to pass information directly to deeper layers, making it easier to train very deep networks.
- **Inception**, a network architecture consisting of several inception modules allowing multiple operations (convolution, pooling) running in parallel (Szegedy, et al., 2015). Also known as GoogLeNet, Inception has been designed by Google to efficiently use computational resources while maintaining high performance in image recognition tasks. The key innovation of the Inception architecture is the *Inception module*, which performs convolution operations with multiple filter sizes (1x1, 3x3, and 5x5) simultaneously within the same module. This multi-scale approach allows the network to capture features at different levels of detail, enhancing its ability to recognize patterns in images. The original Inception model, GoogLeNet, has 22 layers, but subsequent versions, such as Inception-v3 and Inception-v4, have introduced various improvements, including factorized convolutions, auxiliary classifiers, and batch normalization.

The following networks, which had not been mentioned in the ARCAFF proposal, were also identified and selected as most appropriate network architectures from DL literature for AR classification objective:

- **ViT**, Vision Transformer (ViT) is a deep learning architecture introduced by Google that applies the principles of transformers, initially developed for natural language processing (NLP), to computer vision tasks (Vaswani, et al., 2017). Unlike traditional Convolutional Neural networks, ViT processes images by dividing them into a sequence of fixed-size patches. Each patch is then linearly embedded and treated as a token, similar to how words are treated in NLP. The transformer model uses self-attention mechanisms to capture the relationships between these patches, allowing it to learn global features of the image. This approach enables ViT to effectively handle large-scale image data and achieve competitive performance on image classification benchmarks, often surpassing traditional CNNs when trained on sufficient data. ViT's architecture includes multiple layers of transformers, which consist of multi-head self-attention and feed-forward neural networks, making it a powerful tool for various computer vision applications.
- **DeiT**, short for Data-efficient Image Transformers, is a vision transformer model introduced by Facebook AI (Touvron, et al., 2021). It aims at improving the efficiency of vision transformers by training them with significantly less data compared to earlier models. DeiT incorporates a distillation token that leverages knowledge distillation from a CNN teacher model, enhancing the transformer's performance. This approach makes DeiT competitive with state-of-the-art CNNs in terms of accuracy while being more data-efficient
- **Swin Transformer**, short for Shifted Window Transformer and introduced by Microsoft in 2021, addresses some limitations of ViT by enhancing efficiency and scalability (Liu, et al., 2021). The key innovation of the Swin Transformer lies in its hierarchical structure and shifted window approach. It divides the input image into non-overlapping patches, similar to ViT, but processes these patches within local windows. These windows shift at each layer, allowing the model to capture both local and global features effectively. This approach significantly reduces the computational complexity compared to processing the entire image at once, making it more efficient for high-resolution images. The hierarchical nature of Swin Transformer allows it to construct multi-scale feature maps, similar to traditional CNNs, enabling it to be applied to a variety of vision tasks such as image classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation. By combining the strengths of transformers and CNNs, Swin Transformer achieves state-of-the-art performance on several benchmarks while maintaining computational efficiency.

In addition, we also implemented a custom CNN consisting of 5 convolutional layers and a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) with four layers.

As shown in the following section among all the previously cited architectures, the one which shows to have the best performance on the dataset at disposal is the Swin Transformer.

Given the widespread availability of pre-trained weights for many of the architectures described above, we have investigated the potential of leveraging **transfer learning** (Bozinovski & Fulgosi, 1976), (Zoph, 2020) to enhance the performance of our specific task. Transfer learning is a technique that involves utilizing a pre-trained model, originally trained on a large and diverse dataset, as a starting point for a new task. This approach is particularly effective when the source and target domains share similar characteristics, as it allows the model to benefit from previously learned features. Pre-trained models are usually trained on ImageNet (1000 categories on 1.2M hand-labelled images), a large-scale dataset containing millions of natural images of everyday objects, enabling models to learn robust and generalizable features (Deng, et al., 2009). However, in our specific application, magnetogram cutouts of the Sun have domain-specific shapes and patterns distinct from the natural images found in datasets like ImageNet. Consequently, the features learned by models pre-trained on natural images are not directly applicable to our magnetogram data. Despite this, the use of pre-trained weights offers an advantage over starting with random ones as it provides a better initialization point for the model. When models begin training from a pre-trained state, they already possess a wealth of low-level features such as edges, textures, and basic shapes, which are universally useful across various types of images. This head start allows the model to converge more quickly and efficiently during training, as it does not need to learn these fundamental features from scratch.

2.2.1 Implementation

WP3 considered all the previously described learning models and trained them on the original dataset provided by WP2 for solving the two multi-class problems of classification into 6 classes (QS, α , β , β - δ , β - γ , β - γ - δ) or into 4 classes (QS, α , β , β -X), and the binary problem QS vs AR. All results are available and will constitute milestone M4. In the following we will provide implementation details for ViT, our custom CNN and ResNetXX with 18 and 34 layers. In the following subsection we will then provide metrics to evaluate their performances according to the first and third classification problem.

- 1) **ViT**. We used a Vision Transformer configuration designed for image classification, characterized by a base-sized transformer with 16x16 patch size and 224x224 input image resolution. This model utilizes the transformer architecture's ability to capture complex patterns and relationships in image data, offering a powerful alternative to traditional CNN-based image classification models.

Process Flow:

1. Patch Embedding

- a. The input image is divided into 16x16 patches, resulting in $(224/16) \times (224/16) = 14 \times 14 = 196$ patches.
- b. Each 16x16 patch is flattened into a vector and then linearly transformed to a lower-dimensional embedding vector. This process creates a sequence of 196 embedding vectors, each representing a patch.

2. *Positional encodings*

- a. Positional encodings are added to the patch embeddings to retain information about the position of each patch within the original image. This helps the transformer to understand the spatial relationships between patches.

3. *Transformer Encoder*

- a. The sequence of patch embeddings, with positional encodings added, is fed into the transformer encoder.
- b. The transformer encoder consists of multiple layers of self-attention mechanisms and feed-forward neural networks. In the base configuration, there are 12 such layers.
- c. Self-attention allows the model to focus on different parts of the image simultaneously, capturing complex relationships and patterns.

4. *Classification Head*

- a. After passing through the transformer encoder, the output sequence is fed into a classification head.
- b. A special token (often referred to as the CLS token) is used to aggregate information from the entire sequence. The output corresponding to this token is used for the final classification.
- c. A linear layer followed by a softmax activation function typically performs the final classification, outputting probabilities for each class.

2) **Custom CNN.** The custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) has the following configuration.

a) *Convolutional Layers.*

The model consists of five convolutional layers with specific configurations:

- (i) **Units:** Each layer has 128 units.
 - (ii) **Kernel Sizes:** Varying sizes of 7x7, 5x5, and 3x3
 - (iii) **Padding:** Zero padding to maintain the input shape.
 - (iv) **Regularization:** L2 regularization with regularization parameter set to 0.02.
 - (v) **Initializer:** Glorot uniform initializer (Glorot & Bengio, 2010).
 - (vi) **Activation:** ReLU activation function.
 - (vii) **Batch Normalization and MaxPooling:** Applied after each convolutional layer for normalization and dimensionality reduction.
- b) *MLP Layers:* After flattening the output from convolutional layers, the model has 4 fully connected layers with 1024, 512, 256 and 128 units, respectively, using ReLU activation and dropout for regularization.
- c) *Output Layer:* A final dense layer with softmax activation to output probabilities for each class.

- d) *Optimizer*: Adam optimizer (Kingma & Ba, 2014) with a learning rate of $1e-4$.
- e) *Loss Function*: Weighted categorical cross-entropy, where weights are computed to handle class imbalance.
- f) *Metrics*: Accuracy is used as the primary metric.
- g) *Class Weights*: weights are computed to handle class imbalance.
- h) *Early Stopping*: Implemented to halt training if the validation loss does not improve for a fixed number of epochs (200).

3) ResNet. As previously described, ResNet is a deep learning architecture known for its ability to train very deep networks effectively using a technique called residual learning. The key innovation of ResNet is the introduction of residual blocks, which help mitigate the vanishing gradient problem by allowing gradients to flow through skip connections. We have considered two different model configurations, ResNet18 and ResNet34.

ResNet18

- a) **Depth**: 18 layers
- b) **Architecture**:
 - **Convolutional layers**: 7×7 convolutional layer with 64 filters, stride 2, followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation.
 - **MaxPool**: 3×3 max pooling layer with stride 2.
 - **Residual Blocks**: 8 blocks, each consisting of two 3×3 convolutional layers with batch normalization and ReLU activation. The skip connections bypass two layers.
 - **Layers Configuration**:
 - 2 blocks with 64 filters
 - 2 blocks with 128 filters
 - 2 blocks with 256 filters
 - 2 blocks with 512 filters
 - **FC Layer**: Fully connected layer with output size equal to the number of classes.

ResNet34

- a) **Depth**: 34 layers
- b) **Architecture**:
 - **Convolutional layers**: 7×7 convolutional layer with 64 filters, stride 2, followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation.
 - **MaxPool**: 3×3 max pooling layer with stride 2.
 - **Residual Blocks**: 16 blocks, each consisting of two or three 3×3 convolutional layers with batch normalization and ReLU activation. The skip connections bypass two or three layers.

- **Layers Configuration:**
 - 3 blocks with 64 filters
 - 4 blocks with 128 filters
 - 6 blocks with 256 filters
 - 3 blocks with 512 filters
- **FC Layer:** Fully connected layer with output size equal to the number of classes.

Detailed Components:

1. Residual Blocks:

- The core building block of ResNet is the residual block. Each block consists of:
 - **Two 3x3 Convolutional Layers (for ResNet18):** Each layer is followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation.
 - **Three 3x3 Convolutional Layers (for ResNet34):** The deeper configuration includes an additional convolutional layer per block.
 - **Skip Connections:** Directly add the input of the block to the output of the convolutional layers. This helps in the effective training of deeper networks by allowing gradients to bypass one or more layers.

2. Initial Layers:

- Both models start with a 7x7 convolutional layer followed by max pooling. This initial layer is responsible for reducing the spatial dimensions of the input image and extracting basic features.

3. Fully Connected Layer:

- After passing through the residual blocks, the feature maps are average pooled to a smaller spatial size. The final features are then passed through a fully connected layer that outputs the class probabilities.

Training

ResNet models are trained using Adam optimizer with learning rate scheduling and data augmentation.

2.2.2 Performances

For the four learning models described in detail in the previous sub-section, we provide now evaluation of performances with respect to the more complex problem of classification into 6 classes (QS, α , β , $\beta\text{-}\delta$, $\beta\text{-}\gamma$, $\beta\text{-}\gamma\text{-}\delta$). As a metric for evaluating the performances we have used the Validation Accuracy measuring the proportion of correctly classified cases from the total number of objects in the dataset:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Correct predictions}}{\text{All predictions}}$$

It is worth noting that accuracy has its drawbacks. While it does provide an estimate of the overall model quality, it disregards class balance and the cost of different errors. Just like with binary classification, in multi-class classification problems, some classes might be more prevalent and it might be easier for the model to classify them. In this case, high accuracy can be confusing. For the four considered models for our purposes, Table 1 summarizes the number of parameters to be optimized and the rather high values for the Accuracy obtained on a validation set. It is worth noting that, for each model, by changing the number of the network's parameters, the accuracy values are rather stables. This is a strong warning to us that *issues previously reported as being present in the dataset severely limit a model's ability to improve its performance beyond a certain threshold*. We are confident that these values will increase once the models are re-trained on the new version of the dataset.

MODEL	Number of parameters	Validation Accuracy
ViT	86.567.656	0.872
CNN	1.944.966	0.866
ResNet18	11.689.512	0.859
ResNet34	21.797.672	0.864

Table 1 Accuracy values for 4 selected models with respect to the 6-class classification problem.

In addition, for the ViT model, Figure 10 shows the confusion matrix in which each row represents the rate of instances in an actual class while each column represents the rate of instances in a predicted class. The model has no problem in correctly classifying instances from QS and β classes. Instances from α class are split into predicted α and β classes, instances from β - γ class are split into predicted β and β - γ classes and instances from β - γ - δ class are split into β - γ and β - γ - δ classes. The β - δ class is completely misclassified and split into β , β - γ and β - γ - δ classes. Too many instances are assigned to β class.

		Predicted Category					
		QS	Alpha	Beta	Beta-Delta	Beta-Gamma	Beta-Gamma-Delta
Actual Category	QS	98.24	0.73	1	0	0.01	0
	Alpha	5.06	54.13	40.09	0	0.7	0
	Beta	1.4	8.82	82.6	0.24	6.57	0.33
	Beta-Delta	0	0	36.84	2.63	26.31	34.21
	Beta-Gamma	0.33	1.33	46.65	0.5	44.98	6.18
	Beta-Gamma-Delta	0.58	0	14.61	2.33	39.76	42.69

Figure 10 Confusion matrix for the ViT model for the multi-class classification problem.

If the classification task is reduced to the simpler one of discriminating between QS and AR (binary problem) the performance of the ViT model can be described by the confusion matrix of Figure 11 made up of four elements:

- TP** true positives: rate of AR predicted and observed (in this case 97.55%);
- FN** false negatives: rate of AR not predicted but observed (in this case 2.44%);
- FP** false positives: rate of AR predicted but not observed (in this case 1.75%);
- TN** true negatives: rate of AR not predicted and not observed (in this case 98.24%).

		Predicted Category	
		QS	AR
Actual Category	QS	98.24	1.75
	AR	2.44	97.55

Figure 11 Confusion matrix for the ViT model for the binary classification problem.

Many skill scores can be found in literature for the assessment of the binary classification performances. All these scores are linked to the previously defined four elements characterizing the confusion matrix:

True Skill Statistic:

$$TSS = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} - \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

Heidke Skill Score:

$$HSS = \frac{2 \cdot (TP \cdot TN - FN \cdot FP)}{(TP + FN) \cdot (FN + TN) + (TP + FP) \cdot (FP + TN)}$$

Critical Success Index:

$$CSI = \frac{TP}{TP + FN + FP}$$

Recall (or Probability of detection):

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Precision:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Specificity:

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{TN}}{\text{TN} + \text{FP}}$$

Accuracy:

$$\text{ACC} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}$$

F1 score:

$$\text{F1 score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Balanced Accuracy:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{2} (\text{Recall} + \text{Specificity})$$

Table 2 summarizes the values of the previously cited metrics for the binary classification problem (QS vs AR) in the case of the ViT model. As expected, the values are very high with about 5% misclassification errors most likely due to the problems in the dataset, previously reported.

METRIC	Value
TSS	0.9580
HSS	0.9561
CSI	0.9444
Recall	0.9756
Precision	0.9673
Specificity	0.9824
Accuracy	0.9800
F1 score	0.9714
Balanced Accuracy	0.9790

Table 2 Evaluation metrics for the binary classification problem in the case of the ViT model.

3. Active region localisation and classification using full disk magnetograms

3.1 Dataset

In order to achieve the second objective of the project,

Objective 2 (O2) - Active region localisation and classification using full disk magnetograms

WP2 has created a second dataset including full-disk images from HMI magnetograms, and the bounds of the bounding boxes to train supervised region detection models. The dataset consists of a catalogue of 8,268 rows of data, extracted from 3,478 full disk fits files. The catalogue and full disk fits files were put at disposal to WP3 as a single compressed tar archive ‘*arccnet-extraction-dataset-v20231207.tar.gz*’.

For this second dataset, covering the time range from April 30, 2010 to December 29, 2022, we did not perform a statistical analysis as for the first one, we merely investigated the cardinality of classes (Figure 12) and the number of ARs per image as a function of time (Figure 13). The histogram in Figure 12 shows that this dataset too is very unbalanced, with a large number of β instances (about 56% of the dataset) and α (about 32%). β - γ , β - γ - δ and β - δ together reach 12%. As done before, the classes γ and γ - δ have been excluded. Figure 13 roughly corresponds to the red part of Figure 3 (HMI observations) with a peak of 11 ARs during maximum solar activity of cycle 24.

It is also worth noting that this second dataset was released before we became aware of the issues reported in section 2.1.1. Therefore, some of the pathologies reported for the first dataset also afflict this second one, particularly all those that affected the HMI images.

Figure 12 Distribution of the classes in the dataset.

Figure 13 Number of AR as a function of time in each image.

Figure 14 Training set: number of instances for each class, dimension and position of the bounding boxes.

In order to train the deep learning models and to test their performances, the dataset has been divided into training and validation sets, while maintaining the relative proportion between instances of the various classes. In Figure 14 the composition of the training set is shown. In particular the bar plot (upper left panel) shows the number of instances for each class, while the upper right panel shows the sizes of the bounding boxes in the set. The $x - y$ scatter plot on the bottom left panel visualizes the distribution of the bounding box center positions (x, y) , where the axes, ranging from 0 to 1, represent the normalized position of the bounding box center coordinates. The plot shows a relatively even distribution along the x -axis, with more concentration around certain y -values (approximately 0.4 and 0.6), suggesting that ARs are more often localized around these values. Eventually, the width-height scatter plot on the bottom right panel shows the relationship between the width and height of bounding boxes (with again normalized values on the axes). The plot indicates that most bounding boxes have small widths and heights, as indicated by the higher density of points in the lower left corner.

3.2 Deep learning models

In order to achieve *Objective 2*, in the ARCAFF proposal we identified the following CNN architectures from DL literature:

- **R-CNN**, a region-based CCN for object detection extracting region proposals from the input image via selective search, computing CNN features and employing Support Vector Machines (SVM) to classify the object in the region (Girshick, Donahue, T., & Malik, 2016).

Figure 15 R-CNN process flow.

- **Fast R-CNN/Faster R-CNN**, accelerated version of the R-CNN network. In particular Faster R-CNN uses a separate network to predict the region proposals instead of using selective search algorithm (Girshick, Fast R-CNN, 2015) (Ren, He, Girshick, & Sun, 2017)
- **YOLO** (You Only Look Once), using a single convolutional network to predict bounding boxes and associate class probabilities (Redmon, Divvala, Girshick, & Farhadi, 2016), quickly gained popularity for its high speed and accuracy.

3.2.1 YOLOv8

For the tasks of AR localisation and classification, we chose to fine tune on our dataset the YOLO model, in particular the 8-th version of YOLO from Ultralytics. As a state-of-the-art model, YOLOv8 builds on the success of previous versions, introducing new features and enhancements to increase performance, flexibility, and efficiency. It supports a full range of visual AI tasks, including sensing, segmentation, pose estimation, tracking, and classification. This versatility allows users to leverage YOLOv8's capabilities in a variety of applications. The YOLOv8 architecture is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 YOLOv8 architecture (from <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics/issues/189>)

The YOLOv8 architecture is composed of two major parts, namely the *backbone* and the *head*, both of which use a fully convolutional neural network.

- a) **Backbone.** YOLOv8 has a backbone network consisting of multiple convolutional layers organized sequentially to extract relevant features from the input image. The C2f module integrates high-level features with contextual information to improve detection accuracy. The SPPF (Spatial Pyramid Pooling Faster) module (He, Zhang, Ren, & Sun, Spatial Pyramid Pooling in Deep Convolutional Networks for Visual Recognition, 2015), and other subsequent convolution layers, process features at various scales.
- b) **Head.** The head takes the feature maps produced by the Backbone and processes them to provide the final output in the form of bounding boxes and object classes. The head is designed to be *detachable*, which implies that it handles object scores, classification, and regression tasks independently. This approach allows each branch to focus on its own task while improving the overall accuracy of the model. U-layers (Upsampling layers) increase the resolution of the feature maps. The head uses a sequence of convolutional layers to analyse feature maps, followed by a linear layer for predicting the bounding boxes and *class probabilities*. The head design is optimized for speed and accuracy, with emphasis on the number of channels and kernel size of each layer to maximize performance. Eventually, the Detection module uses a series of convolution and linear layers to map high-dimensional features to bounding boxes and object classes.

The entire structure is designed to be quick and effective, while maintaining high accuracy in object detection. In YOLOv8, there are five different models available for each category of detection, segmentation, and classification. According to the number of parameters to be optimized (right panel of Figure 17), YOLOv8 Nano is the smallest and fastest model, while YOLOv8 Extra Large (YOLOv8x) is the slowest yet most accurate model among them:

- **Nano** (n): 3.0 million parameters
- **Small** (s): 11.1 million parameters
- **Medium** (m): 25.9 million parameters
- **Large** (l): 43.6 million parameters
- **Extra Large** (x): 68.2 million parameters

From a computer performance point of view, the number of Floating point Operations Per Second (FLOPS) increases as the complexity of the model increases, as shown in the left panel of Figure 17, where the numbers refer to computations performed on a machine with the following characteristics:

- **OS:** Ubuntu focal 20.04 x86_64
- **CPU:** Intel® Xeon® Processor E5-2698 v4
- **GPU:** 4 x NVIDIA Tesla V100 DGXS 32GB
- **RAM:** 256GB

Figure 17 Number of GFLOPs required (left panel) and number of parameters to be optimized (right panel) in each of the 5 available models for YOLOv8.

3.2.1.1 AR localisation and classification: test images

In this subsection we provide a few examples of AR detection both successful and unsuccessful. In all cases the given full disk magnetograms fits files have been resized to a dimension of 640x640 to fit the input size of the YOLOv8 model. All experiments have been tracked using *Comet*, a cloud-based experiment management platform that provides a comprehensive suite of tools for tracking, visualizing, and comparing machine learning experiments. In the provided dataset, plage regions are not labelled, so during training those are interpreted as background. In all the following examples, the left panel shows the input image with the boxes to be identified and associated labels highlighted, while the right panel shows the result of the localization and classification process completed by YOLOv8.

Test 1: hmi.m_720s.20140114_000000_TAI.1.magnetogram.png

In the input image three different ARs are present (two α -type and one β -type). All three ARs are correctly detected and classified, with very high class probability, by YOLOv8.

Figure 18 Example of multi-class correct detection and classification, with high class probability.

Test 2: hmi.m_720s.20221019_000000_TAI.3.magnetogram.png

In the input image two different ARs are present, both of which are β . The model correctly identifies both regions and associates the correct label. However, the morphologically more extended and complex AR is associated with a class probability of less than 50%.

Figure 19 Example of multi-class correct detection and classification, but with low class probability for one of the two classes.

Test 3: hmi.m_720s.20101022_000000_TAI.1.magnetogram.png

In the input image just one α AR is present. The model correctly identifies the location and class with high class probability.

Figure 20 Example of single-class correct detection and classification with high class probability.

Test 4: hmi.m_720s.20110513_000000_TAI.1.magnetogram.png

In the input image just one β AR is present. The model correctly identifies the location and class with high class probability.

Figure 21 Example of single-class correct detection and classification with high class probability.

Test 5: hmi.m_720s.20140312_000000_TAI.1.magnetogram.png

In the input image two different ARs are present, one α -type and one β -type. The model is unable to identify either of them.

Figure 22 Example of no detection.

Test 6: hmi.m_720s.20100610_000000_TAI.1.magnetogram.png

In the input image two different ARs are present (β and β - γ). The model correctly identifies both regions but the associated labels are not correct, although classified with associated high class probability.

Figure 23 Example of multi-class correct detection but wrong classification.

Test 7: hmi.m_720s.20220303_000000_TAI.3.magnetogram.png

In the input image, there is simultaneously an unlabelled plage and an AR with associated label. The model mistakenly localizes and classifies the plage as an AR and does not localize the true AR.

Figure 24 Example of plage detected and classified as AR and, at the same time, true AR not localized.

Test 8: hmi.m_720s.20221113_000000_TAI.3.magnetogram.png

In the input image there is a single β - γ AR. The model localizes it twice, with two overlapping boxes and with two different labels, β and β - γ . The highest probability is associated with the wrong class.

Figure 25 Example of single-class detected in overlapping boxes and classified with different labels.

3.2.1.2 AR localisation and classification: performances

As in the case of AR classification described before, defining metrics for evaluating model performance is a key tool for quantitatively assessing accuracy and efficiency in identifying and locating objects of interest within images. This information is critical for evaluating and improving model performance.

For the specific task of identifying objects in images, very useful metrics are:

- **Intersection over Union (IoU):** The IoU is a measure quantifying the overlapping between a predicted bounding box and a ground truth bounding box. It plays a key role in assessing the accuracy of object location.
- **Precision and Recall:** Precision and Recall have been already introduced in Section 2.2.2. Precision quantifies the percentage of true positives among all positive predictions, evaluating the model's ability to avoid false positives. On the other hand, Recall computes the percentage of true positives among all actual positives, measuring the model's ability to detect all instances of a class.
- **Average precision (AP):** AP computes the area under the Precision-Recall curve, providing a single value that encompasses the precision and recall performance of the model.

- **Mean Average Precision (mAP):** mAP generalizes the definition of AP to multi-class object detection problems by computing mean AP values over multiple classes of objects. In particular we distinguish between:
 - **mAP50:** Mean Average Precision computed at an IoU threshold of 0.50. It's a measure of the model's accuracy considering only the easy detections, and
 - **mAP50-95:** Average of the mAP computed for different varying IoU thresholds, ranging from 0.50 to 0.95. It provides a comprehensive view of the model's performance at different levels of detection difficulty.
- **F1 score:** The F1 score has been introduced in Section 2.2.2. too. It is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, and provides a balanced assessment of a model's performance by considering both false positives and false negatives.

Defining the step as the logarithm of the batch size (that is the number of training samples to work through before the model's parameters are updated), Figure 26 shows the behaviours of mAP50, mAP50-95, Precision and Recall as a function of the step for the 5 different YOLOv8 models at disposal, during the training phase. The performances of the different models are very similar with respect to the mAP50, Precision and Recall: by increasing the computational complexity of the model, performance increases very marginally. This ceiling effect is probably mainly due to the presence of plages, which being implicitly stated as background do not allow the network to learn beyond a certain point. As for the mAP50-95, the xlarge model seems to offer better performances, as confirmed in Table 2 where the final values are summarized.

Figure 26 mAP50 (upper left panel), mAP50-95 (upper right panel), recall (bottom left panel) and Precision (bottom right panel) behaviours as a function of the step, for the 5 different YOLOv8 models.

MODEL	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall
YOLOv8n	0.55	0.42	0.56	0.50
YOLOv8s	0.55	0.44	0.59	0.53
YOLOv8m	0.56	0.47	0.57	0.55
YOLOv8l	0.55	0.47	0.61	0.49
YOLOv8x	0.55	0.48	0.55	0.54

Table 3 mAP50, mAP50-95, Precision and Recall final values for the 5 YOLOv8 models.

For the xlarge model we now report some specific results.

Figure 27 shows the **Precision-Recall curve** where, in the x -axis, Recall values (ranging from 0 to 1) measure the proportion of true positive detections out of all actual positives while, in the y -axis, Precision values (ranging again from 0 to 1) measure the proportion of true positive detections out of all positive detections made by the model. Looking at the different curves:

- **β - γ - δ class** (purple line) maintains high precision across a wide range of recall values, suggesting good performance for this class;
- **β - δ class** (red line) shows very poor performance with low precision and recall values, indicating again significant challenges in detecting this class accurately;
- **β class** (orange line) has a relatively good performance with high precision at moderate recall values;
- the **all classes** (thick blue line) curve shows a general trend of decreasing precision with increasing recall, which is typical for most models.

Figure 27 Precision-Recall curve. Legend provides information on each curve along with their mAP50 values.

In Figure 28 we present the confusion matrix in which each row represents the rate of instances in an actual class while each column represents the rate of instances in a predicted class.

	Predicted Category					
Alpha	51.24	22.34	1.58	0	0	24.83
Beta	8.65	66.18	6.81	0.26	1.83	16.25
Beta-Gamma	0.75	24.24	44.69	0	4.54	25.75
Beta-Delta	7.69	38.46	23.07	7.69	7.69	15.38
Beta-Gamma-Delta	4.65	2.32	6.97	2.32	53.48	30.23
background	37.79	50.74	7.64	1.06	2.76	0

Figure 28 Confusion matrix associated to YOLOv8x model performances.

As a last result, Figure 29 shows the Pairplot, a graph commonly used to visualize the pairwise relationships between variables in a dataset. In this setting, this pairplot shows the distribution and relationships between the bounding box parameters of the detected objects: x , y , width, and height.

The diagonal elements of the pairplot show the distribution (histograms) of each (normalized) variable, where

- x is the horizontal position of the bounding box's center;
- y is the vertical position of the bounding box's center;
- **Width** is the width of the bounding box;
- **Height** is the height of the bounding box.

The histograms show that x positions are relatively evenly distributed across the image width, while the y positions show a bimodal distribution with more detections in the middle of the two solar hemispheres. The widths of the bounding boxes are mostly small, with a long tail towards larger values. The heights of the bounding boxes also show a similar distribution to the widths, with most values being small.

The off-diagonal elements show the pairwise relationships between the variables using scatter plots, where each plot represents a pair of variables, with the density of points shown by the colour. In particular:

- the scatter plot x vs y shows the distribution of the bounding box centers across the image. There seems to be a relatively uniform distribution horizontally, while vertically, there are some concentrated bands, indicating that objects might be more frequently detected at certain vertical positions;

- the scatter plots of x vs $width$ and y vs $width$ show the relationship between the center positions and the widths of the bounding boxes. The width values appear to be more concentrated towards smaller values;
- the scatter plots of x vs $height$ and y vs $height$ show the relationship between the center positions and the heights of the bounding boxes. Similar to the width, the height values are also more concentrated towards smaller values;
- the $width$ vs $height$ scatter plot shows the relationship between the widths and heights of the bounding boxes. There's a notable correlation whereby larger widths tend to come with larger heights, which makes sense as larger objects would typically have both larger width and height values.

Figure 29 Pairplot associated to YOLOv8x model performances.

4. Summary

In this report the Deep Learning models for Active Region Classification and Active Region localisation and Classification have been described.

4.1 Active region classification

To accomplish the AR classification task, AlexNet, Visual Geometry Group, ResNetXX, Inception, Vision Transformer (ViT), Data-efficient Image Transformer, Swin Transformer and a custom CNN have been studied. Four of these models (ViT, custom CNN, ResNet18 and ResNet34) have been optimized and trained on the dataset released from WP2. Their performances have been evaluated through well know metrics and skill scores (confusion matrices, TSS, HSS, CSI, Recall, Precision, Specificity, Accuracy, F1score, Balanced Accuracy). The results are quite satisfactory, although the skill score values do not improve significantly even by increasing the number of model hyper-parameters. A deep analysis of the dataset at disposal showed the presence of possible sources of mistakes: overlapping ARs boxes, AR labelled even beyond the solar limb, AR labelled as Quiet Sun (place regions), images with horizontal bars, magnetograms deemed bad for different reasons (corrupted images, images with swirling effects, noise images and rotated images). We believe that the presence of such problems may limit the performance of the models.

Some of these problems can be solved and WP2 has already worked to fix this kind of issues by releasing a new, updated version of the dataset. The training of DL models on the new dataset is ongoing. Unfortunately, other types of problems such as class imbalance, overlapping regions, unlabelled region cannot be resolved and, to handle the specific problems we have, we will investigate novel losses or ad-hoc training schemes. For instance, advanced loss functions such as hinge loss and others that have been used in the literature to deal with very large class imbalance in the so called *long-tail learning* will be tested.

4.2 Active region localisation and classification

For the AR localisation and classification task, R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, Faster R-CNN and YOLO models have been studied. Among them we chose to fine tune the YOLO model, in particular the Ultralytics YOLOv8 model, characterized by an architecture supporting a full range of artificial intelligence tasks. According to the number of parameters to be optimized (ranging from a minimum of 3 million to a maximum of 68 million), YOLOv8 is available in 5 different versions (nano, small, medium, large, extra-large). We considered all possible configurations and evaluated the performances of the models with the metrics provided by the DL literature for the specific task of identifying objects in images (Precision, Recall, Mean Average Precision, mAP50, mAP50-95). The identification of objects in images is a more complicated task than simple classification, which is why the values obtained for the metrics are lower than in the previous case. The model that seems to give the best results is the most complex version of YOLOv8 (extra-large). However, it is worth emphasising that even this second database shares some of the problems encountered in the first one, which may limit the

performance of the models. Even in this second case, a new version of the database, purged of fixable problems, will be released from WP2 and the models will be trained on it again. In parallel with the use of the new dataset, we will also investigate the use of loss functions for unbalanced and long-tailed data as well as new specific machine learning solutions to handle data with the issues highlighted in our case.

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